

Evaluation of heavy metal concentrations in seven commercial marine fishes caught in the Mediterranean coast of Morocco and their associated health risks to consumers

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ABSTRACT

To evaluate the health risk of some heavy metals attributed to the consumption of common edible fish species which were available for consumers. The concentrations of Cd, Pb, Cu, Fe, Zn, Ni and Cr were determined in muscles, gills and livers, of seven common edible fish species, namely (*Octopus vulgaris* cuvier (1797), *Sardina pilchardus*, *Trachurus trachurus*, *Palaemon serratus*, *Sparus aurata*, *Dicentrarchus labrax* and *Solea vulgaris*) gathered from the Mediterranean coast in the North East of Morocco, landed in the port of Nador during the autumn and spring of the year 2016. Concentrations of heavy metals were determined by inductively coupled plasma- atomic emission spectroscopy and expressed as mg/kg of dry matter. Results showed that iron and zinc were the most abundant among all fish tissues under investigation. The data obtained in the present work were compared with the counterpart data reported internationally. The estimated values of all metals in muscles of fish in this study were below the admissible values. It can be concluded that the investigated metals in edible parts of the examined species have no health problems for consumers.

KEYWORDS

consumers; daily intake; fish species; heavy metals; Mediterranean coast; target hazard quotient

1. INTRODUCTION

The aquatic environment comprises the major part of our environment and resources. Therefore, its safety is directly related to human health. The excessive contamination of aquatic ecosystems has evoked major environmental and health concerns worldwide (McNeil and Fredberg, 2011). Heavy metal contamination has been identified as a concern in coastal environment, due to discharges from industrial wastes, agricultural and urban sewage. Metals are

accumulated in the marine organisms through a variety of pathways, including respiration, adsorption and ingestion. Metals such as iron, copper, zinc and manganese, are essential metals since they play an important role in biological systems. On the other hand, mercury, lead and cadmium are non-essential metals which are toxic in nature are also present in trace amounts. The essential metals can also produce toxic effects when the concentration of metal is excessively elevated. Fish and mussels are the major part of the human diet and it is not surprising that several studies have been carried out on metal accumulation in

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different fish species (Türkmen et al., 2013).

Fish are an important aquatic source of food chain, which are found in aquatic ecosystems. Fish are also used as a good indicator of heavy metals and various other elemental contaminations. Aquaculture is one of the newest fields of fisheries for food production. Considering the nutrition factor, fish have a nutritional value because it contains not only proteins but also omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids of two types, Docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) and Eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA). For regular development, Omega-3 (n-3) fatty acids are very essential, where they prevent preterm delivery, stroke and heart disease by reducing cholesterol levels. Fish also perform an essential role in human health because they contain minerals and vitamins. Fish contains several trace metals, such as Zn, Fe, Ca, Cd, Pb and Cu. Moreover, the intake of fish is beneficial to children's growth and development and helps to fight against some diseases such as rheumatoid arthritis, psychiatric disorders and lung disease (Rehulka, 2002). In contrast to the potential health benefits of dietary fish intake, the chemical pollutants contained in these products have emerged an issue of concern, particularly for frequent fish consumers (Martorell et al., 2011).

In this regard, heavy metals have the tendency to accumulate in various organs of aquatic organisms, especially in fish which in turn may enter into the human metabolism through consumption which cause serious health problems (Bravo et al., 2010). Metals such as Zn, Fe, Cu and Mn are essential elements. They may produce toxic effects when their levels exceed certain limits in organisms (Schroeder HA.,1973). Nwaedozi (1998) reported that Zn contamination affects the hepatic distribution of other trace metals in fish. Zn,

Cu and Mn, which are essential elements, compete for the same site in animals. This will undoubtedly affect tissue metals concentrations as well as certain important physiological processes. Therefore, many consumers regard any presence of these metals in fish as a hazard to health. Fish are integral component of human diet. They need to be carefully screened to ensure that unnecessarily high levels of heavy metals will not be transferred to human population through consumption of contaminated fish (Rahman et al., 2012).

In Morocco, there are not enough studies on the heavy metal content in these commercially available marine fishes. Consequently, it seemed necessary to study the concentrations of these metals in the edible tissues of these species in order to evaluate the risks related to the consumption of this product. Our study is therefore interested in the evaluation of the content in seven metallic elements (Cd, Pb, Fe, Cu, Zn, Ni and Cr) in the samples of (*Octopus vulgaris* cuvier (1797), *Sardina pilchardus*, *Trachurus trachurus*, *Palaemon serratus*, *Sparus aurata*, *Dicentrarchus labrax* and *Solea vulgaris*) gathered from the Mediterranean coast in the North East of Morocco, landed in the port of Nador during the autumn and spring of the year 2016. We have retained this species because they are mostly consumed by the population and perhaps these species can be considered as a sentinel organism and bio-indicator of pollution in this area. In addition, we study the health risk assessment of metals attributed to consumption of these marine fish species available in our markets.

Figure 1. Location of the studied site (Google maps)

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Fish sampling

Octopus vulgaris cuvier (1797), *Sardina pilchardus*, *Trachurus trachurus*, *Palaemon serratus*, *Sparus aurata*, *Dicentrarchus labrax* and *Solea vulgaris* were selected as bioindicator; because these species are widely consumed by Moroccans. The individuals of these species were taken at the level of Mediterranean Sea (port of Nador) (Figure 1).

The studied site extends over a coastline of 153 km (UAN, 2011). This site is influenced by freshwater flowing watershed of wadis especially in period of floods. Inter alia, the province of Nador accounts 170 industrial units. The ventilation by branch reveals a predominance of the chemical and para-chemical industry with 58 units, followed by the agrifood industry, mechanical, metallurgical industry, textile, leather and electrical industry, which generate industrial waste loaded with chemical products.

2.2. Preparation and treatment of samples

The samples of *Octopus vulgaris* cuvier 1797, *Sardina Pilchardus*, *Trachurus Trachurus*, *Palaemon Serratus*, *Sparus aurata*, *Dicentrarchus labrax* and *Solea vulgaris* were obtained by the anglers from when they landed. Three individuals per sample were stored in plastic bags and conserved at -20 °C. To avoid any contamination by the environment or the sampling equipment, the procedures of sampling were performed according to the procedure described in the Aminot manual (Aminot and Chaussepied, 1983).

In the laboratory, the samples of *Octopus vulgaris* cuvier (1797), *Sardina pilchardus*, *Trachurus symmetricus*, *Palaemon Serratus*, *Sparus aurata*, *Dicentrarchus labrax* and *Solea vulgaris* were dissected. We studied the three parts of these species: The liver, the gills and the muscle, were taken separately and then dried at 80 °C to constant weight. Then they were finely grounded using an agate mortar to avoid any external contamination by heavy metals. A quantity varying between 0.5 g and 1 g of dry weight of the biological material was used for analysis of the following metals: lead, copper, zinc, iron, cadmium, chromium, and nickel. The mineralization was realized in two steps (Cheggour, 1989): calcination at 550 °C for 4h followed by an acid treatment at ambient temperature overnight, followed by digestion at 60 °C for 2 h. Then the samples were subjected to membrane

filtration "Millipore" 0.45 microns of porosity. The filtrate obtained is diluted with ultrapure water, and then the samples are stored in polypropylene bottles at 4 °C until the analysis. The metallic elements studied were determined by inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-AES).

2.3. Quality control of the results

To take account of the matrix effect that can sometimes induce important analytical errors, reference materials (SRM: NIST 1566b) were used for the calibration of the measures. These samples were treated in the same conditions as our samples. Control samples were used in parallels. The results of the recovery percentages of the four metallic elements in the reference materials used are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Recovery of various heavy metals of certified reference materials (CRMs)

NIST 1566 (CRM : oyster tissue)		
	Target	% Recovery
Cadmium	4.2 ± 0.4	107
Copper	66 ± 4	97
Zinc	830 ± 57	95
Iron	921 ± 59	89
Lead	0.35 ± 0.13	102.86
Chromium	0.77±1.18	96.97
Nickel	2.50±0.19	85.20

SD-M-2 / TM (CRM: marine sediment); NIST 1566 (CRM: oyster tissue); (mg/g dry weight)

2.4. Calculation of the daily intake of metals

The daily intake was calculated based on the concentration of heavy metals in the muscles in order to determine the extent of exposure through fish consumptions.

The estimated daily intake (EDI) of metals for adults in (mg/kg/day) was determined by the following equation:

$$EDI = (C_{\text{metal}} \times W_{\text{fish}}) / (B_w) \quad (1)$$

where, C_{metal} is the concentration of heavy metals in studied fish samples (mg/kg, on fresh weight basis); W_{fish} represents the daily average consumption of fish in this region (kg/day); and B_w is the body weight of an adult (kg).

Table 2. RfDo values,mg/kg body weight/day (USEPA 2000)

	Cr	Ni	Cu	Zn	Cd	Pb	Fe
RfDo	3x10 ⁻³	2x10 ⁻²	4x10 ⁻²	3x10 ⁻¹	1x10 ⁻³	4x10 ⁻³	7x10 ⁻¹

2.5. Health risk assessment

By comparing the daily intake (concentration in fishes and times when the amount is consumed) with the chronic oral reference dose (RfDo), it is possible to determine whether a person is exceeding acceptable health guidance levels (Patrick et al., 2008). RfDo values are shown in Table 2.

THQ is a ratio of determined dose of a pollutant to the dose level (RfDo). It is used at health risk assessment in order to determine the carcinogenicity of the samples. The below formula suggested was applied in the calculation of THQ (Islam et al., 2014).

$$THQ = \frac{Efr \times EDtot \times FIR \times C}{RfDo \times BWa \times ATn} \times 10^{-3} \quad (2)$$

In Eqn. 2, Efr stands for frequency of exposure (365 days/year), EDtot for period of exposure (average life expectancy: 70 years), FIR for food intake rate (g/day), C for the heavy metal concentration in fish muscular tissue (mg/kg), RfDo for oral reference dose (mg/kg/day), BWa for average adult body weight (70 kg), ATn for period of average exposure for non-carcinogenic part of elements (365 days/year x number of exposure years 70 years). If the THQ value obtained is below “1”, an adverse effect for human health can be excluded considering the elements studied. The below total THQ (TTHQ) formula suggested by (Chien et al., 2002) was used in the determination of the total risk of heavy metals.

$$TTHQ = THQ \text{ (toxicant 1)} + THQ \text{ (toxicant 2)} + \dots + THQ \text{ (toxicant n)} \quad (3)$$

2.6. Statistical Analysis

All data generated were analyzed statistically by calculating the mean and standard deviation of the measured parameters. The coefficient of variation of the metals was also calculated.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The accumulation of heavy metals (Cd, Pb, Fe, Cu, Zn, Ni and Cr) in the samples of gills, liver and the muscle of the *Octopus vulgaris cuvier (1797)*, *Sardina pilchardus*, *Trachurus trachurus*, *Palaemon serratus*, *Sparus aurata*, *Dicentrarchus labrax* and *Solea vulgaris* in the Mediterranean coast from the North East of Morocco during the autumn and spring of the year 2016, analysed and represented in Table 3 and Figures 2 and 3. The results are expressed in milligrams of the element studied per gram of dry matter (mg/kg DM).

According to the results obtained and the graphs represented above, it was noticed that there were differences in the concentrations of the studied metals between different organs and between species. Fe, Zn and Cu were the most abundant in all the examined organs.

3.1. Cadmium (Cd)

Cadmium does not have an essential role in biological process in living organisms. It is widely known to be a highly toxic non-essential heavy element. Thus, even at its low concentration, Cd could be harmful to living organisms. (Tsui and Wang, 2004). The levels of cadmium are generally low (Figures 2 and 3), the highest value is in the range of 0.138 mg/kg obtained in the digestive gland of *O. vulgaris* studied in the spring season, while the lowest content is in the range of 0.00209 mg/kg obtained in the gills of *S. pilchardus* studied in the autumn season. According to these concentrations, we can establish an order of accumulation of Cd in the fish samples during autumn and spring seasons as follows:

-In autumn: *O. vulgaris* > *S. aurata* > *S. vulgaris* > *D. labrax* > *S. pilchardus* > *T. trachurus* > *P. serratus*.

-In spring: *O. vulgaris* > *S. aurata* > *D. labrax* > *S. pilchardus* > *T. trachurus* > *S. vulgaris* > *P. serratus*.

In other words, the digestive gland seems to be the organ, which accumulates the highest value of Cd especially in the case of the octopuses. The concentration of cadmium in the present study were generally in similar ranges with literature, where it was reported that the levels were also low in comparison to

Figure 2. The concentrations of heavy metals (mg/kg) in fish samples from the study area in autumn

0.58-1.26mg/100g recorded in fishes of Olomoro Water body (Idodo, 2002), and between 0.001 and 0.009 mg/kg in eleven species of fishes in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil (Medeiros et al., 2012). These values remain lower than those found in the Red Sea of Egypt whose concentration is extremely high (8.37 ± 0.32 mg/kg) in the liver of *Caranx* sp. (Shalateen) (El-Moselhy et al., 2014). Despite this level of presence, heavy metal concentrations in our study in both seasons are much lower than the maximum limit fixed by the WHO, which is about 0.3 mg/kg.

3.2. Lead (Pb)

Lead is a toxic element, which can affect fish in high doses, lead to a decrease in survival, growth rates, development and metabolism and to the increased mucus formation. Pb may have many adverse health effects including neurotoxicity and nephrotoxicity (Yimaz et al., 2010).

The highest value of Pb in this study is in the range of 0.0245mg/kg obtained in the gills of *S. aurata* studied in the autumn season, while the lowest content

Figure 3. The concentrations of heavy metals (mg/kg) in fish samples from the study area in spring

is in the range of 0.002610 mg/kg obtained in the muscle of *P. serratus* studied in the spring season. According to these concentrations, we can establish an order of accumulation of Pb in the fish samples during autumn and spring seasons as follows:

- In autumn: *S. aurata* > *O. vulgaris* > *S. pilchardus* > *D. labrax* > *T. trachurus* > *P. serratus* > *S. vulgaris*
- In spring: *S. aurata* > *O. vulgaris* > *S. pilchardus* > *D.*

labrax > *T. trachurus* > *S. vulgaris* > *P. serratus*. The seasonal variation of the metal concentrations in organs can be explained in terms of their bioavailability and their presumed role in the physicochemical parameters of the environment (pH, salinity, temperature). Other authors have shown lower levels, with concentrations ranging from 0.01 to 0.02 mg/kg in the fish of the Adriatic Sea (Bilandžić et al., 2011), from 0.04 to

Table 3a. Heavy metals concentration in the tissues of the fish species studied in mg/kg of the dry matter

Seasons	Species	C(Cd)×10 ⁻³	C(Pb)×10 ⁻³	C(Zn)×10 ⁻³	C(Cu)×10 ⁻³	C(Fe)×10 ⁻³	C(Cr)×10 ⁻³	C(Ni)×10 ⁻³
Autumn	<i>-S. vulgaris</i>							
	Muscle	5.42±0.004	10.69±0.007	183.43±0.09	14.54±0.009	470.78±0.03	14.51±0.01	4.31±0.002
	Liver	10.92± 0.013	4.41±0.001	204.80±0.05	34.56±0.009	172.09±0.1	7.26±0.008	9.67±0.01
	Gills	8.88± 0.008	7.27±0.003	126.04±0.05	48.89±0.04	176.08±0.09	11.80±0.01	12.35±0.01
	CV%	33.07	42.16	23.75	52.82	62.75	32.73	170.29
	<i>-P. serratus</i>							
	Muscle	3.12± 0.001	12.77±0.01	199.03±0.08	60.13±0.021	643.03±0.04	13.45±0.01	7.98±0.007
	<i>-S. pilchardus</i>							
	Muscle	2.69± 0.001	11.80±0.01	174.18±0.03	34.26±0.004	556.37±0.08	7.77±0.09	5.6±0.003
	Liver	5.15± 0.003	10.27±0.008	73.87±0.07	36.75±0.004	199.94±0.05	4.11±0.02	4.31±0.001
	Gills	2.09± 0.001	19.44±0.01	115.67±0.02	36.31±0.0005	441.74±0.01	3.44±0.0008	4.59±0.003
	CV%	48.98	35.50	41.55	3.71	45.56	45.64	14.03
	<i>-T. trachurus</i>							
	Muscle	3.47± 0.001	5.27±0.001	79.11±0.03	33.97±0.005	537.74±0.1	12.24±0.01	4.58±0.0007
	Liver	4.08± 0.0009	17.49±0.01	98.23±0.05	20.93±0.015	598.56±0.07	14.65±0.01	8.24±0.002
	Gills	2.22± 0.001	9.68±0.007	137.26±0.04	30.15±0.009	616.41±0.1	10.34±0.01	3.88±0.008
	CV%	29.11	57.22	28.26	23.64	7.05	17.40	42.06
	<i>- S. aurata</i>							
	Muscle	12.72± 0.01	11.52±0.006	144.18±0.04	34.81±0.001	265.36±0.1	10.69±0.007	14.71±0.01
	Liver	12.01± 0.01	6.24±0.002	162.22±0.05	31.97±0.01	511.50±0.07	8.02±0.007	11.98±0.01
	Gills	2.81± 0.001	24.57±0.01	71.63±0.02	27.47±0.01	250.40±0.1	10.33±0.008	3.44±0.009
	CV%	60.21	66.87	38.05	11.78	42.81	14.96	58.53
	<i>- D. labrax</i>							
	Muscle	3.12± 0.0009	18.60±0.01	130.85±0.02	76.33±0.02	336.14±0.07	19.44±0.01	4.70±0.002
	Liver	2.08± 0.001	15.69±0.01	190.13±0.09	245.37±0.06	607.29±0.04	23.05±0.01	71.24±0.009
	Gills	9.85± 0.01	10.66±0.007	228.21±0.14	65.84±0.02	547.88±0.06	8.33±0.009	2.12±0.001
	CV%	84.07	26.80	26.80	77.99	28.67	45.28	150.58
	<i>-O. vulgaris</i>							
	Muscle	8.74± 0.009	23.74±0.01	158.44±0.01	50.40±0.03	253.91±0.05	18.19±0.01	3.47±0.001
	Digestive gland	4.77± 0.004	18.74±0.01	61.03±0.01	30.33±0.02	240.25±0.06	10.83±0.01	2.49±0.003
	Gills	13.84± 0.01	19.44±0.01	227.83±0.09	31.10±0.01	324.18±0.09	13.92±0.01	3.80±0.001
	CV%	49.87	13.11	56.19	30.50	16.50	25.82	20.94
	Maximum limit WHO/ FEPA (mg/kg)	0.3	0.3	30	3	0.5	0.6	1

0.3 mg/kg in the fish of Rio de Janeiro (Medeiros et al.,2012), and from 0.04 mg/kg to 0.28 mg/kg in the liver and the gills of European catfish (*Silurus glanis*) of Italian rivers (Squadrone et al.,2013). However, all the found contents remain below the standard fixed by the WHO which is 0.3 mg/kg.

3.3. Zinc

Zinc is one of the most important trace elements for normal growth and development of humans. Its deficiency results from inadequate dietary intake, impaired absorption, excessive excretion

or inherited defects in Zn metabolism. Moreover, Zn is also considered as highly bioavailable in the aquatic environment and thus may exhibit higher accumulation in various tissues (Zhao et al., 2012). The toxicity of zinc is rare, but it can be toxic above the limit of 30 mg /kg. Overall, the accumulation of the

zinc in the studied species does not show significant differences. The highest concentration was observed in the digestive gland of the *O. vulgaris* studied in the spring with a value of 1.189 mg/kg, and the lowest concentration is 0.0610 mg/kg noted in the digestive gland of the *O. vulgaris* studied in the autumn season,

Table 3b. Heavy metals concentration in the tissues of the fish species studied in mg/kg of the dry matter

Seasons	Species	C(Cd)×10 ⁻³	C(Pb)×10 ⁻³	C(Zn)×10 ⁻³	C(Cu)×10 ⁻³	C(Fe)×10 ⁻³	C(Cr)×10 ⁻³	C(Ni)×10 ⁻³
Spring	<i>-S. vulgaris</i>							
	Muscle	3.33±0.0007	12.77±0.01	120.43±0.08	15.96±0.01	80.49±0.05	3.73±0.0007	4.20±0.003
	Liver	3.26±0.001	7.63±0.003	157.83±0.06	9.37±0.007	556.56±0.4	8.88±0.009	10.41±0.01
	Gills	3.50±0.001	4.79±0.002	161.98±0.09	23.88±0.03	800.07±0.4	7.08±0.006	3.02±0.001
	CV%	3.6	48.17	15.59	44.29	76.40	39.82	67.55
	<i>-P. serratus</i>							
	Muscle	2.88±0.001	2.61±0.001	1018.479±0.8	97.94±0.1	492.93±0.3	16.62±0.02	16.10±0.01
	<i>-S. pilchardus</i>							
	Muscle	13.60±0.01	4.70±0.002	302.91±0.003	18.74±0.015	367.56±0.2	4.44±0.0004	3.30±0.0008
	Liver	3.24±0.001	3.24±0.001	214.49±0.15	13.38±0.015	5007.27±0.7	9.85±0.012	2.16±0.001
	Gills	3.88±0.0004	4.58±0.003	223.17±0.14	35.10±0.05	113.37±0.05	11.38±0.012	4.22±0.003
	CV%	84.05	19.42	19.74	50.49	150.59	42.61	31.98
	<i>-T. trachurus</i>							
	Muscle	3.81±0.0003	5.41±0.003	196.19±0.04	4.51±0.001	149.70±0.06	2.52±0.001	2.59±0.001
	Liver	3.15±0.0009	10.80±0.01	419.75±0.1	6.06±0.005	721.57±0.5	3.88±0.0004	3.12±0.001
	Gills	11.59±0.01	3.33±0.0007	494.71±0.3	14.71±0.01	766.38±0.1	3.74±0.0007	3.33±0.0008
	CV%	75.91	59.19	41.94	65.22	62.98	22.13	12.65
	<i>- S. aurata</i>							
	Muscle	3.74±0.0007	11.38±0.01	115.38±0.1	13.88±0.01	255.50±0.2	3.18±0.0008	2.88±0.002
	Liver	2.95±0.001	2.91±0.001	197.05±0.06	15.69±0.02	5951.86±0.6	8.74±0.009	3.40±0.0007
	Gills	12.49±0.01	3.33±0.001	156.88±0.02	12.49±0.01	477.79±0.08	7.49±0.006	4.27±0.002
	CV%	82.81	83.56	26.10	11.44	144.79	45.08	19.97
	<i>- D. labrax</i>							
	Muscle							
	Liver	2.76±0.001	4.44±0.002	78.62±0.01	14.09±0.01	516.05±0.03	5±0.002	3.59±0.0006
	Gills	3.88±0.0004	3.19±0.001	165.77±0.07	271.76±0.4	511.55±0.2	3.61±0.001	4.44±0.002
	CV%	3.74±0.0004	3.33±0.0007	142.95±0.04	8.67±0.009	543.72±0.1	17.91±0.01	3.29±0.001
		17.63	18.74	35.00	153.15	3.32	89.20	15.80
	<i>--O. vulgaris</i>							
	Muscle	5.69±0.0004	5.97±0.005	71.05±0.002	22.77±0.03	526.68±0.04	3.44±0.001	3.47±0.0006
	Digestive gland	138.78±0.1	14.99±0.01	1189.68±0.9	772.02±0.9	695.40±0.5	3.24±0.001	3.58±0.0005
	Gills	13.19±0.001	11.10±0.01	145.37±0.06	49.29±0.07	361.74±0.03	3.47±0.0006	14.44±0.01
	CV%	142.27	42.33	133.45	151.09	31.60	3.69	87.97
	Maximum limit WHO/FEPA (mg/kg)	0.3	0.3	30	3	0.5	0.6	1

Table 4. EDIs of metals via consumptions of fish muscles in mg/kg/day during the autumn season

Species	Cd	Pb	Zn	Cu	Fe	Cr	Ni
<i>S. vulgaris</i>	2.0829x 10 ⁻⁶	4.1243x10 ⁻⁶	7.0755x10 ⁻⁵	5.6086x10 ⁻⁶	0.00018	1.665x10 ⁻⁶	1.665x10 ⁻⁶
<i>P. serratus</i>	1.2052x10 ⁻⁶	4.9278x10 ⁻⁶	7.6769x10 ⁻⁵	2.3193x10 ⁻⁵	0.00024	4.767x10 ⁻⁶	2.163 x10 ⁻⁶
<i>S. pilchardus</i>	1.0029x10 ⁻⁶	4.5528x10 ⁻⁶	6.7187x10 ⁻⁵	1.3216x10 ⁻⁵	0.00024	2.163x10 ⁻⁶	1.767 x10 ⁻⁶
<i>T. trachurus</i>	1,3114x10 ⁻⁶	2.035x10 ⁻⁶	3.0515x10 ⁻⁵	1.3105x10 ⁻⁵	0.00020	1.767x10 ⁻⁶	5.677 x10 ⁻⁶
<i>S. aurata</i>	4.8986x10 ⁻⁶	4.4457x10 ⁻⁶	5.5616x10 ⁻⁵	1.3427x10 ⁻⁵	0.00010	5.677x10 ⁻⁶	1.815 x10 ⁻⁶
<i>D. labrax</i>	1.1957x10 ⁻⁶	7.177x10 ⁻⁶	5.0474x10 ⁻⁵	2.944x10 ⁻⁵	0.00012	1.815x10 ⁻⁶	1.33 x10 ⁻⁶
<i>O. vulgaris</i>	0.00001944	9.159x10 ⁻⁶	6.1116x10 ⁻⁵	1.944x10 ⁻⁵	9.79x10 ⁻⁵	1.339x10 ⁻⁶	4.767 x10 ⁻⁶

Table 5. EDIs of metals via consumptions of fish muscles in mg/kg/day during the spring season

Species	Cd	Pb	Zn	Cu	Fe	Cr	Ni
<i>S. vulgaris</i>	1.2855x10 ⁻⁶	4.9277 x10 ⁻⁶	4.6453x10 ⁻⁵	6.1597x10 ⁻⁶	3.1046x10 ⁻⁵	1.4408 x10 ⁻⁶	1.623 x10 ⁻⁶
<i>P. serratus</i>	1.1141 x10 ⁻⁶	1.0069 x10 ⁻⁶	0.00039284	3.777x10 ⁻⁵	0.00019013	6.412 x10 ⁻⁶	6.2133 x10 ⁻⁶
<i>S. pilchardus</i>	5.2491 x10 ⁻⁶	1.8157 x10 ⁻⁶	0.00011684	7.231 x10 ⁻⁶	0.00014178	1.714 x10 ⁻⁶	1.274 x10 ⁻⁶
<i>T. trachurus</i>	1.4729 x10 ⁻⁶	2.0889 x10 ⁻⁶	7.5677 x10 ⁻⁵	1.742 x10 ⁻⁶	5.774x10 ⁻⁵	9.7484 x10 ⁻⁷	1.001 x10 ⁻⁶
<i>S. aurata</i>	1.4462 x10 ⁻⁶	4.3921 x10 ⁻⁶	4.4507 x10 ⁻⁵	5.356 x10 ⁻⁶	9.8553x10 ⁻⁵	1.226 x10 ⁻⁶	1.114 x10 ⁻⁶
<i>D. labrax</i>	4.8206 x10 ⁻⁶	1.7140 x10 ⁻⁶	3.0326 x10 ⁻⁵	5.4366 x10 ⁻⁶	0.00019905	1.928 x10 ⁻⁶	1.3873 x10 ⁻⁶
<i>O. vulgaris</i>	2.1985 x10 ⁻⁶	2.3032 x10 ⁻⁶	2.7405 x10 ⁻⁵	8.7843 x10 ⁻⁶	0.00020315	1.328 x10 ⁻⁶	1.3391 x10 ⁻⁶

Table 6. THQs for individual metals by consumptions of fish muscles during the autumn season

Species	Cd	Pb	Zn	Cu	Fe	Cr	Ni
<i>S. vulgaris</i>	0.0021	0.00097	0.0002	0.0001	0.0002	0.001	0.00008
<i>P. serratus</i>	0.0034	0.0012	0.0002	0.0005	0.0003	0.0017	0.0001
<i>S. pilchardus</i>	0.001	0.0011	0.0002	0.0003	0.0003	0.0011	0.0001
<i>T. trachurus</i>	0.0013	0.0005	0.0001	0.0003	0.0003	0.0015	0.00008
<i>S. aurata</i>	0.0049	0.0011	0.0001	0.0004	0.0001	0.0013	0.0002
<i>D. labrax</i>	0.0012	0.0018	0.0001	0.0007	0.0001	0.0025	0.00009
<i>O. vulgaris</i>	0.0034	0.0023	0.0002	0.0004	0.0001	0.0023	0.00006

Table 7. THQs for individual metals by consumptions of fish muscles during the spring season

Species	Cd	Pb	Zn	Cu	Fe	Cr	Ni
<i>S. vulgaris</i>	0.001	0.0012	0.0001	0.0001	0.00004	0.0004	0.00008
<i>P. serratus</i>	0.0011	0.0002	0.0013	0.0009	0.0002	0.002	0.0003
<i>S. pilchardus</i>	0.0053	0.0004	0.0002	0.0009	0.0002	0.0005	0.0006
<i>T. trachurus</i>	0.0014	0.0005	0.0006	0.00004	0.00008	0.0003	0.00005
<i>S. aurata</i>	0.0014	0.0011	0.0002	0.0001	0.0001	0.0004	0.00005
<i>D. labrax</i>	0.0010	0.0004	0.0001	0.0001	0.0002	0.0006	0.00007
<i>O. vulgaris</i>	0.002	0.0005	0.00009	0.0002	0.0002	0.0004	0.00006

According to these levels, we can establish an order of accumulation of Zn in the fish samples taken during autumn and spring seasons as follows:

-In autumn: *D. labrax* > *P. serratus* > *S. vulgaris* > *S. pilchardus* > *S. aurata* > *T. trachurus* > *O. vulgaris*.
 -In spring: *O. vulgaris* > *P. serratus* > *T. trachurus* >

S. pilchardus > *S. aurata* > *D. labrax* > *S. vulgaris*.

Furthermore, these levels remain much lower than those given by the WHO, and comparing with those found by other authors from 337 to 246.15 and 18.96 in 39.59 mg/kg respectively for the liver and the gills of fishes of the Egyptian Mediterranean Sea (Khaled, 2013). From 27.5 to 28.2 mg/kg for fish of the Bay of Iskenderun, Turkey (Yilmaz et al., 2010), and from 3.5 to 53.5 mg/kg for fish of the Aegean and the Mediterranean Sea (Türkmen et al., 2009).

3.4. Copper (Cu)

Copper is one of the metals, which is essential to human health. It is present in the aquatic environment due to accumulation of domestic and agricultural wastes. Copper combines with certain proteins to produce enzymes that act as catalyst to help in the body functions and it is also necessary for the synthesis of haemoglobin (Sivaperumal et al., 2007). The toxicity of copper is rare, but it can be toxic above the limit of 3 mg /kg. The highest concentration was observed in the digestive gland of the *O. vulgaris* studied in the spring with a value of 0.7720 mg/kg, and the lowest concentration is 0.0045 mg/kg noted in the muscle of the *T. trachurus* studied in the spring season, According to these levels, we can establish an order of accumulation of Cu in the fish simples during autumn and spring seasons as follows:

-In autumn : *D. labrax* > *P. serratus* > *S. vulgaris* > *O. vulgaris* > *S. pilchardus* > *S. aurata* > *T. trachurus*.

-In spring: *O. vulgaris* > *D. labrax* > *P. serratus* > *S. pilchardus* > *S. vulgaris* > *S. aurata* > *T. trachurus*.

These copper contents are lower in this study compared to 4.19 to 5.64 mg/kg. For fish of Iskenderun Bay of Turkey (Yilmaz et al., 2010), 1.05 to 2.56 and 1.20 to 5.90 mg/kg respectively for muscle and gills of fishes of the Egyptian Mediterranean (Khaled ,2013), 0.23 to 1.47mg/kg in fish from the Adriatic Sea (Bilandžić, 2011), and 1.2 to 2.9 mg /kg in fishes of Rio de Janeiro (Medeiros et al., 2012).

3.5. Iron (Fe)

Iron is involved in the haemoglobin synthesis in the red blood corpuscles of the blood. It is a necessary element in human diet and plays a significant role in metabolic processes (Dallman, 1986). In this study, the observed mean value of Fe in the fish parts far exceeded the WHO/FEPA recommended limits of 0.5 mg/kg in fish foods, with a value of 5.951 mg/kg. The highest content is obtained in the liver of the *S. aurata* studied in the

spring season and the lowest concentration is 0.080 mg/kg noted in the muscle of *S. vulgaris* studied in the spring season. According to these levels, we can establish an order of accumulation of Fe in the fish simples during autumn and spring seasons as follows:

-In autumn: *P. serratus* > *T. trachurus* > *D. labrax* > *S. pilchardus* > *S. aurata* > *S. vulgaris* > *O. vulgaris*.

-In spring: *S. aurata* > *S. pilchardus* > *S. vulgaris* > *T. trachurus* > *O. vulgaris* > *D. labrax* > *P. serratus*.

However, an essential heavy metal, Fe has the tendency to become toxic to living organisms, even when exposure is low. Iron concentrations in the present study were highest than the literature where iron levels mainly ranged between 0.6 and 0.7 mg/L accumulated in the soft part of the sea urchin *Paracentrotus lividus* of the Mediterranean littoral of Saidia (Fahssi and Chafi, 2015).

3.6. Chromium (Cr):

Chromium is an essential trace metal. The biologically usable form of chromium plays an essential role in glucose metabolism. It has been estimated that the average human requires nearly 1 µg/day (Abdallah, 2013). The highest concentration was observed in the liver of the *D. labrax* studied in the autumn season with a value of 0.0230/kg and the lowest concentration is 0.00252 mg/kg noted in the muscle of the *T. trachurus* studied in the spring season, According to these levels, we can establish an order of accumulation of Cu in the fish simples during autumn and spring seasons as follows:

-In autumn : *D. labrax* > *S. aurata* > *O. vulgaris* > *T. trachurus* > *S. vulgaris* > *P. serratus* > *S. pilchardus*.

-In spring: *D. labrax* > *P. serratus* > *S. pilchardus* > *S. vulgaris* > *S. aurata* > *T. trachurus* > *O. vulgaris*.

The present Cr concentrations were comparable to those reported from Masoud et al. (Masoud et al. 2007) with 0.23-1.26, 1.02-5.71 and 0.39-3.22 µg/g for fish from Alexandria coastal waters, Egypt, for muscle, liver and gill tissues, respectively. The maximum guideline, 12-13 µg/g, stipulated by the United States Food and Drug Administration was higher than the concentrations of Cr measured in all the fish samples used in this study. The present study revealed that the concentrations of Cr in the species of fish studied were not consistently higher than the WHO/FEPA recommended limits.

3.7. Nickel (Ni)

The biological role of nickel is uncertain. It can affect plant growth and has proved essential for some species.

Some nickel compounds can cause cancer if the dust is inhaled, and some people are allergic to contact with this metal (Chivers, 2015). In this study the highest concentration was observed in the liver of the *D. labrax* studied in the autumn season with a value of 0.0712 mg/kg and the lowest concentration is 0.0021 mg/kg noted in the gills of the *D. labrax* studied in the autumn season, According to these levels, we can establish an order of accumulation of Cu in the fish samples during autumn and spring seasons as follows:

-In autumn: *D. labrax* > *O. vulgaris* > *S. aurata* > *S. vulgaris* > *T. trachurus* > *P. serratus* > *S. pilchardus*.

- In spring: *P. serratus* > *O. vulgaris* > *S. vulgaris* > *D. labrax* > *S. aurata* > *S. pilchardus* > *T. Trachurus*.

The nickel concentrations in this study are very low, and they aren't dangerous neither for the species nor for human health. The results found in this study are similar to those reported by other authors, Murtala et al., 2012 reported absence of Cr in the liver and muscles of some fish, whereas Eralagere and Bhadravathi, (2008) assessed 0.039 to 0.44 mg Cr/kg in liver and muscles, respectively of *Oreochromis mossambicus* in Jannapura lake of India.

3.8. Daily intake of metals

The potential health risks associated with fish consumptions may be linked to the carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic effects. Heavy elements may present in low levels in the water reservoirs. However, fish species can concentrate these contaminants by bioaccumulation and bio magnifications (Kalay et al., 1999). Fish consumption is a major source of human exposure to the above mentioned contaminants. Therefore, fish consumers can accumulate high levels of these contaminants in their bodies. According to the Moroccan Ministry of Fishing, Moroccans have an average consumption per person (70 kg in body weight) of 27.39 g /day.

An important aspect in assessing associated risks to human health from potentially harmful chemicals in food is the knowledge of the dietary intake of such substances, which must remain within determined safety margins. For Fe, Cu, Zn, Cd and Pb, the WHO has established "safe" intake levels i.e., provisional tolerable daily intake levels of 800, 500, 1000, 1, and 3.57 µg/kg of body weight, respectively, and 3 µg/kg for the Chromium (FAO and WHO, 2004). In this study, the daily intake of metals through the consumptions of muscles was lower than the WHO's "safe" provisional tolerable daily intake guideline levels for Cd, Cr, Cu, Fe, Ni, Pb and Zn. Tables 4 and

5 illustrate EDIs of metals via consumptions of fish muscles in mg/kg/day during the autumn and spring season, respectively.

3.9. Health risk assessment

Information on fish consumption is essential for assessing potential public health risk associated with eating contaminated fish (Copat et al., 2012). Because fish are nutritious, readily available and relatively inexpensive, hence they are broadly consumed. However, contaminated fish can contribute to metal poisoning (USEPA, 2004). We assessed the risk associated with consuming fish from the Mediterranean coast of Morocco by calculating the THQs for individual metals by consumptions of fish muscles during the autumn and spring season (Tables 6 and 7).

The THQ is a ratio of determined dose of a pollutant to a reference dose level. If the ratio is less than 1, the exposed pollution is unlikely to experience obvious adverse effects. The THQ has been recognized as a useful parameter for evaluation of risk associated with the consumptions of metal contaminated food (Abdallah, 2013). The THQs values of Cd, Cr, Cu, Fe, Ni, Pb and Zn for the investigated fishes do not exceed one indicating so that there is no health risk from consuming.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The present study provides valuable data on metal levels in the tissues of the surveyed fish species and directly indicates the environmental contamination of the Mediterranean coast of Morocco. In addition, it provides information about the possible risks associated with consumption of the fish examined. Thus the comparison of the concentrations registered in these species studied shows that the concentrations of trace elements(Fe, Zn, Cu) are higher compared to those of toxic elements (Pb and Cd). The seasonal variation of the concentration of heavy metals could be particularly attributed to the physiological processes, including those of the reproduction as well as the variation of certain environmental factors (salinity, temperature) which have a role in the bioavailability of these heavy metals released by the sediment. Besides our results prove that the concentrations of different heavy metals in the studied species with the exception of iron are very low and don't exceed the standards set by the World Health Organization. It can be concluded

that these metals in edible parts of the examined species have no health problems for consumers in our study. In general, routine check and frequent analysis of food stuff is required to avoid the risk of exceeding the intake beyond the tolerance limits standards. Moreover, the results of this work can also be used to understand the chemical quality of fishes and to evaluate the possible risk associated with their consumptions.

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